

Tuning N-Heterocyclic Carbenes in T-Shaped Pt^{II} Complexes for Intermolecular C–H Bond Activation Reactions of Arenes

Orestes Rivada-Wheelaghan, Manuel A. Ortuño, Josefina Díez, Agustí Lledós* and Salvador Conejero*

Dedicated to Professor Guy Bertrand on the occasion of his 60th birthday

C–H bond activation reactions of hydrocarbons promoted by Pt^{II} complexes have been intensively studied since Shilov's first report on the catalytic conversion of methane into methanol and methyl chloride by PtCl₄²⁻ salts.^[1] Mechanistically, the first step of this process, prior to C–H bond cleavage of methane, is coordination of the hydrocarbon to the platinum centre, and this might occur either associatively or with prior dissociation of a coordinated ligand. Although in most cases studies the C–H bond activation at Pt^{II} centers seem to take place by an associative mechanism,^[1b] there are theoretical and experimental evidences in good agreement with a dissociative pathway involving the formation of transient T-shaped 14-electron Pt^{II} species.^[2] Some of these coordinatively unsaturated highly electrophilic species have been isolated and crystallographically characterized,^[3] and a few of them undergo *intramolecular* C–H bond activation (cyclometallation) reactions. Nevertheless, we are not aware of *intermolecular* C–H bond cleavage of hydrocarbons induced by stable T-shaped Pt^{II} complexes. Recently, we have described the synthesis of highly electrophilic species of this kind stabilized by agostic interactions with N-heterocyclic carbene (NHC) ligands.^[4] Herein, we report that altering the environment of the NHC ligands allows for fine tuning of the steric and electronic properties of their platinum complexes, enabling intermolecular C–H bond activation of some arenes.^[5]

Previously,^[4] we prepared the unsaturated, cationic Pt^{II}

compounds [PtMe(IPr)₂][BARf₄], **2b**, and [Pt(NHC')(NHC)][BARf₄], where NHC' represents the cyclometallated ligands I'Bu (**3a**) and IPr (**3b**). The I'Bu species **2a** converts rapidly into **3a** and cannot be isolated (Scheme 1A). Following a similar synthetic method, namely reaction of [PtMe₃]₄ with the corresponding NHC ligand, followed by treatment with NaBARf₄, the analogous complexes of the IMes* (**2c** and **3c**) and IMes (**2d** and **3d**) NHCs have been prepared and characterized (Scheme 1B).

Scheme 1. (A) Structural representations of compounds **2b** and **3a-b**, described in ref. 4. (B) Synthesis of the cyclometallated complexes **3c-d**.

The Lewis acidic behaviour of the cationic compounds **2b-c** and **3a-c** becomes evident in their reactions with acetonitrile to generate the corresponding colourless adducts [PtMe(NHC)₂(NCMe)][BARf₄] (NHC = IPr, **4b**; IMes* = **4c**) and [Pt(NHC')(NHC)(NCMe)][BARf₄] (NHC = I'Bu, **5a**; IPr, **5b**; IMes*, **5c**) respectively (where NHC' represents the cyclometallated NHC ligand).

Compounds **3a** and **3b** do not react with benzene after prolonged heating at 120 °C. Under these conditions, the I'Bu derivative, **3a**, remains unaltered, while the IPr analog, **3b**, undergoes β-H elimination from one of the *iso*-propyl substituents to afford the cationic complex **6** (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. β-H elimination process for complex **3b**.

[*] O. Rivada-Wheelaghan, Dr. S. Conejero
Instituto de Investigaciones Químicas (IIQ) - Departamento de Química Inorgánica
CSIC / Universidad de Sevilla
Avda. Américo Vespucio 49, 41092 Seville (Spain)
Fax: (+34)954460565
E-mail: sconejero@iiq.csic.es

M. A. Ortuño, Prof. A. Lledós
Departament de Química
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)
Edifici Cn, 08193 Cerdanyola del Vallès (Spain)
Fax: (+34)935812920
E-mail: agusti@klingon.uab.es

Prof. J. Díez
Departamento de Química Orgánica e Inorgánica
Universidad de Oviedo
C/ Julián Clavería 8, 33006 Oviedo (Spain)

[**] Financial support from the Junta de Andalucía (project No. FQM-3151) and the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (projects CTQ2011-23336, CTQ2010-17476 and CONSOLIDER-INGENIO 2010 CSD2007-00006, FEDER support) is acknowledged. O. R.-W. and M. A. O. thank the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación for a research grant. The authors thank Prof. Ernesto Carmona for helping discussions.

Supporting information for this article is available on the WWW under <http://www.angewandte.org> or from the author.

In contrast with this observation, ^1H NMR studies of the reaction of the IMes* complex **3c** and C_6H_6 (120 °C, 4h) reveal the formation of the phenyl derivative **7c**, in *ca.* 4:1 ratio with respect to **3c** (Scheme 3). Prolonged heating at this temperature does not alter the proportion of these compounds. In fact heating a pure sample of **7c** (isolated by fractional crystallization; see SI) in C_6H_6 at 120 °C, gives also rise to a *ca.* 4:1 ratio of **7c**:**3c**. In turn, employing heptane as the solvent allows full conversion back to **3c** and concomitant elimination of C_6H_6 (120 °C, 1h). Clearly **3c** and **7c** exists in an equilibrium which is characterized by thermodynamic parameters $\Delta\text{H} = 4 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta\text{S} = 13 \text{ cal mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (measured in neat C_6H_6 for the equilibrium of **7c** with **3c**, *i.e.* from right to left in Scheme 3, in the temperature range 100-140 °C).

Scheme 3. C–H bond activation of aromatic compounds leading to complex **7c**.

For the analogous IMes compound **3d**, C–H activation is less favourable and only 1-2% of the corresponding phenyl derivative can be detected by ^1H NMR under similar conditions. Finally, it is worth mentioning that blocking the vacant (or accessible) coordination site of **3c** by utilizing its NCMe adduct **5c**, inhibits benzene C–H activation and formation of **7c**.

DFT calculations using PBE0 functional^[6] were performed to study the benzene C–H bond activation with cyclometallated complexes **3a-d**. Gas-phase optimizations of **3a** and **3b** show respectively δ and ζ intramolecular, agostic interactions at the vacancy, as was found experimentally.^[4] Conversely the geometry of the mesityl family of reactants, **3c** (Figure 1) and **3d**, corresponds with a pure T-shaped structure: no agostic interactions with NHC substituents are present.

Figure 1. Gas-phase DFT optimized structure of **3c**. Bond distances in Å and angles in degrees. Selected hydrogens have been omitted for clarity.

This structural difference can be explained by geometrical constraints of the NHC ligands (see the optimized geometries in Figure S2, SI). The second sp^3 carbon atom of *iso*-propyl and *tert*-butyl groups provides flexibility to establish agostic interactions filling the vacancy whereas the planar carbon skeleton of mesityl groups avoids this kind of interaction. Neither agostic interactions are found in the products of benzene C–H bond activation **7a-d**.^[7]

All C–H bond activation processes proceed via oxidative addition and reductive elimination mechanism through unstable Pt^{IV} intermediates **11a-d** but the energy profiles are notably different depending on the NHC ligand (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Energy profiles for the C–H bond activation of benzene with NHC-complexes **3a-d** (relative energies in benzene solvent in kcal mol^{-1}).

For complexes containing *t*Bu and IPr, **3a** and **3b**, the reaction has high energy barriers ΔE^\ddagger (more than 40 kcal mol^{-1}) and in addition is thermodynamically disfavoured. On the other hand complexes containing IMes* and IMes ligands show feasible reaction barriers of *ca.* 30 kcal mol^{-1} . The barriers heights are closely related to the distortion energies ΔE_d^\ddagger , *i.e.*, the energy required by the cyclometallated complexes to adopt the TS-geometry. For transition states regarding **3a** and **3b** this energy is 20.1 and 20.6 kcal mol^{-1} whereas for **3c** and **3d** the energy is 9.6 and 9.0 kcal mol^{-1} . Thus for IMes* and IMes complexes the distortion energy is around 10 kcal mol^{-1} lower than for *t*Bu and IPr ones and this difference is directly reflected on the energy barrier. Removing the agostic interaction in **3a** and **3b** by constrained optimizations accounts for about 2 kcal mol^{-1} (that is *ca.* 10%) of distortion energies. Due to the branched nature of the ligand arms the vacant position is still unreachable after removing this weak interaction and a large ligand distortion is required to create a free space for the benzene molecule. The calculated buried volume^[8] associated with each NHC ligand reflects this behaviour, indicating the higher steric hindrance of *t*Bu and IPr ligands (Table S1, SI). In agreement with experiments, the thermodynamic of the reaction suggests that the product **7c** should be found together with the reactant **3c** whereas the product **7d** could be hardly detected. The different behaviour of IMes* and IMes ligands regarding the product stabilization is an electronic effect that can be attributed to the slightly different basicities of both ligands (Scheme S1 and Table S2, SI).

To complete this study we have explored the reactivity of **3c** toward toluene^[9] and some fluorinated aromatic hydrocarbons. As shown in Scheme 4, toluene experiences regioselective activation at the *meta* and *para* sites, to yield a *ca.* 5:1 mixture of *m*-8:*p*-8. Similarly to C_6H_6 , an equilibrium is established that appears to be

insensitive to the nature of the aromatic hydrocarbon. As found also for the benzene reaction system, heating compounds **8** in heptane at 120 °C results in elimination of toluene and regeneration of the starting compound **3c**.

Scheme 4. C–H bond activation of toluene.

To throw light on the regioselectivity pattern of the toluene activation process, all possible products were calculated using **3c** as reactant (Scheme S2, SI). Only *m*-**8** and *p*-**8** are slightly more stable than **3c**, in agreement with the ratio of products experimentally observed. The thermodynamic origin of the selectivity has been confirmed by calculating the energy reaction profiles of toluene activation in *meta* and *para* positions (Figure S8, SI).

Pentafluorobenzene, C₆F₅H, and 1,2,4,5-tetrafluorobenzene, C₆F₄H₂, experience under similar conditions chemoselective C–H (and not C–F^[10]) activation, giving rise to related aryl complexes **9** and **10** respectively. Once again, equilibria between **3c** and **9** or **10**, which are scarcely affected by the nature of the aryl group, are attained. Studies aimed at understanding this unexpected observation are presently under way. At this stage, it seems possible that steric hindrance exerted by the bulky IMes* groups may destabilize the fluorinated aryl complexes **9** and **10**, comparatively over phenyl species **7c**.

Crystals of the tetrafluorophenyl compound **10** suitable for X-ray studies have been obtained (Figure 3). Beyond any doubt, the most striking feature in the structure of **10** is the lack of agostic or anagostic interactions^[11] involving the methyl groups of the IMes* ligand. Indeed, the closest Pt⋯H–C contacts are of *ca.* 3.117 Å and 3.912 Å, respectively, and lay out of the metal coordination plane. Therefore,

Figure 3. Molecular structure of **10** by X-ray crystallography. BAR₄^f anion has been omitted for clarity.

complex **10** is strictly a T-shaped, 14-electron Pt^{II} complex with no additional stabilization other than steric. The isolation of these kind of platinum complexes is extremely rare, with only one report on Pt-boryl species.^[3b,c]

In summary, the unsaturated 14-electron, T-shaped Pt^{II} complex [Pt(IMes*)₂(IMes*)][BAR₄^f] activates the C–H bonds of aromatic hydrocarbons, including some fluoro derivatives, to provide the corresponding pure T-shaped Pt^{II} aryl species. The flexibility of the NHC ligand, the comparatively lower steric hindrance and excellent electronic properties of the IMes* ligand, and to a lesser extent the lack of agostic interactions in its complex, are responsible for this reaction to occur.^[12] These results highlight how subtle modifications of the NHC ligands in the coordination sphere of a metal complex can direct the reaction favouring a C–H bond activation reaction.

Received: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Published online on ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Keywords: • Agostic interactions • C–H bond activation • DFT • N-heterocyclic carbenes • Platinum • T-shaped complexes

- [1] a) A. Vedernikov, *Chem. Commun.* **2009**, 4781-4790; b) M. Lersch, M. Tilset, *Chem. Rev.* **2005**, *105*, 2471-2526; c) U. Fekl, K. I. Goldberg, *Adv. Inorg. Chem.* **2003**, *54*, 259-320; d) J. A. Labinger, J. E. Bercaw, *Nature* **2002**, *417*, 507-514; e) A. E. Shilov, G. B. Shul'pin, *Chem. Rev.* **1997**, *97*, 2879-2932; f) R. H. Crabtree, *Chem. Rev.* **1995**, *95*, 987-1007.
- [2] a) D. H. Ess, W. A. Goddard III, R. A. Periana, *Organometallics* **2010**, *29*, 6459-6472; b) A. Paul, C. B. Musgrave, *Organometallics* **2007**, *26*, 793-809; c) M. R. Plutino, L. M. Scolaro, A. Albinati, R. Romeo, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2004**, *126*, 6470-6484; d) R. L. Brainard, W. R. Nutt, T. R. Lee, G. M. Whitesides, *Organometallics* **1988**, *7*, 2379-2386.
- [3] a) S. H. Crosby, G. J. Clarkson, J. P. Rourke, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *131*, 14142-14143; b) H. Braunschweig, K. Radacki, K. Uttinger, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2008**, *14*, 7858-7866; c) H. Braunschweig, K. Radacki, D. Rais, D. Scheschke, *Angew. Chem.* **2005**, *117*, 5796-5799; *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2005**, *44*, 5651-5654; d) M. Ingleson, M. F. Mahon, A. S. Weller, *Chem. Commun.* **2004**, 2398-2399; e) W. Baratta, S. Stoccoro, A. Doppiu, E. Herdtweck, A. Zucca, P. Rigo, *Angew. Chem.* **2003**, *115*, 109-113; *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2003**, *42*, 105-108; f) N. Carr, L. Mole, A. G. Orpen, J. L. Spencer, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.* **1992**, 2653-2662.
- [4] O. Rivada-Wheelaghan, B. Donnadieu, C. Maya, S. Conejero, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2010**, *16*, 10323-10326.
- [5] Intermolecular aromatic C–H bond activation promoted by 16-electron Pt^{II} complexes is well established. See for example: a) K. A. Grice, W. Kaminsky, K. I. Goldberg, *Inorg. Chim. Acta* **2011**, *369*, 76-81; b) F. Zhang, C. W. Kirby, D. W. Hairsine, M. C. Jennings, R. J. Puddephatt, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2005**, *127*, 14196-14197; c) S. Reinartz, P. S. White, M. Brookhart, J. L. Templeton, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2001**, *123*, 12724-12725; d) L. Johansson, M. Tilset, J. A. Labinger, J. E. Bercaw, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2000**, *122*, 10846-10855.
- [6] This functional correctly describes the uniform electron gas (UEG) limit, leading to an accurately reproduction of agostic bonding situations. D. A. Pantazis, J. E. McGrady, F. Maseras, M. Etienne, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2007**, *3*, 1329-1336.
- [7] Test calculations on **7c** were performed using M06 functional to weight up possible π⋯π interactions (Figure S7, SI).
- [8] A. C. Hillier, W. J. Sommer, B. S. Yong, J. L. Petersen, L. Cavallo, S. P. Nolan, *Organometallics* **2003**, *22*, 4322-4326.
- [9] a) L. Johansson, O. B. Ryan, C. Romming, M. Tilset, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2001**, *123*, 6579-6590; b) B. Butschke, H. Schwarz, *Organometallics* **2011**, *30*, 1588-1598.
- [10] E. Clot, O. Eisenstein, N. Jasim, S. A. McGregor, J. E. McGrady, R. N. Perutz, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2011**, *44*, 333-348.
- [11] For a definition of agostic and anagostic interactions see: M. Brookhart, M. L. H. Green, G. Parkin, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **2007**, *104*, 6908-6914.
- [12] S. Würtz, F. Glorius, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2008**, *41*, 1523-1533.

Entry for the Table of Contents (Please choose one layout)

Layout 2:

((Catch Phrase))

Orestes Rivada-Wheelaghan, Manuel A. Ortuño, Josefina Díez, Agustí Lledós,* Salvador Conejero* _____ **Page**
– **Page**

Tuning N-Heterocyclic Carbene Ligands in T-Shaped Pt^{II} Complexes for Intermolecular C-H Bond Activation Reactions of Arenes

T-shaped Pt(II) complexes with less flexible substituents on N-heterocyclic carbene ligands allow for C–H bond activation reactions of aromatic compounds. The less branched nature of the NHC substituents prevents agostic interactions and reduces the barriers to achieve the C–H bond cleavage in these unsaturated species.